

Instructional Supervisory Practices and their Support of Teacher Performance: Basis for the Development of a Training Program

Chrysler S. Balmes¹, Gerry S. Digo²

^{1,2} Sorsogon State University Graduate School, Sorsogon City, Philippines.

ABSTRACT

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This study focused on the instructional supervisory practices of school heads as a basis for the development of a training program. It aimed to identify the instructional supervisory practices employed by school heads; determine how these practices influence teachers' performance and professional growth; and develop a training design that will lead to enhanced instructional supervision. The study employed a descriptive qualitative research design and utilized an interview guide for interviews with school heads and teachers. Data gathered was analyzed through reflexive thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and themes. Findings revealed that instructional supervisory practices were evident but varied in implementation in all schools, resulting in differences in teacher performance and professional support. Effective practices identified included instructional monitoring, coaching, mentoring, classroom observation, and facilitation of professional learning activities, which contributed to teachers with positive impact, especially in instructional improvement and confidence. However, they lack continuous and organized professional development, which affects the effectiveness of instructional supervision. Based on the findings, researchers developed a training program entitled "Leading with Impact: Enhancing Instructional Supervision Practices for School Heads." The study concluded that although school heads demonstrate commitment to instructional supervision, there is a strong need for a more systematic, organized, and sustainable approach to strengthen supervisory practices and improve teacher performance and instructional quality.

KEYWORDS:

Instructional Supervision, Leadership Practices, Learning, and Development, Training Program

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is widely recognized as a basic human right and an important foundation for sustainable development. Yet access to quality learning opportunities remains a global challenge. In response to this challenge, the United Nations established Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which aims to ensure inclusive, equitable, and quality education while promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. In the school settings, the acquirement of SDG 4 is largely induced by effective school leadership, where school heads play a crucial role in enhancing teaching quality, supporting teacher professional development, and promoting inclusive and conducive learning environments.

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in education as revealed by Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) (Albert et al., 2023). These results show the necessity to elevate school education leadership. Instructional supervision has been central in increasing teacher competence, refining classroom practices, and finally increasing student learning outcomes. Nevertheless, poor or inadequate instructional leadership has been a major obstacle in the attainment of the reforms that have been projected in national education policies and legislative requirements. Lesson supervisory practices are the key to school heads creating a school environment that is supportive of professional growth, accountability, and teaching excellence. This discussion investigates the legal and policy underpinnings of instructional supervision, the central supervisory practices used by school leaders, and how such practices influence and support the teaching quality and learning environment within the Philippine setting.

The legal basis of instructional supervision in the Philippines is the Republic Act No. 9155, also referred to as

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the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, which institutionalizes school-based management and the accountability of school heads in ensuring quality instruction. The school heads are specifically identified as instructional leaders in the law tasked with the responsibility of overseeing the teaching process and teacher development. In line with this requirement, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the Philippine Professional Standards of School Heads (PPSSH) using DepEd Order No. 024, series of 2020, and defines the areas of leadership and competencies required to be effective in instructional supervision, such as instructional leadership, professional development, and performance management (Kipasika, 2024). The next, even stronger reinforcement of this policy trend is the so-called 70/30 principle, which urges school heads to allocate more of their time toward instructional leadership roles rather than administrative ones (Kilag & Sasan, 2023). This policy orientation can be explained by the fact that DepEd acknowledges that long-term involvement of instructional supervision is critical in enhancing classroom practice and student achievement.

Empirical research confirms the beneficial role of competent instructional leadership on the performance of schools and the quality of teaching (Arrieta, 2021). However, several studies also demonstrate that certain implementation challenges still exist, such as excessive administrative workload, limited time to observe classrooms and coach, and lack of professional development resources (Chin et al., 2022; Kilag and Sasan, 2023). These challenges often affect the consistent performance of supervisory duties despite the presence of clear policy guidelines, indicating a gap between policy intent and performance. These facts underline the importance of exploring the operationalization of instructional supervision on a school level and the way these practices could be reinforced with the help of specific interventions.

Some of the typical instructional supervisory activities utilized by school heads would be classroom observation, coaching, feedback, mentoring, and involvement in Learning Action Cells (LACs). Classroom observation is one of the main tools of instructional quality monitoring and evidence-based feedback provided to teachers, which allows for reflecting and constantly improving practice. Coaching and mentoring also contribute to professional learning by promoting collaborative relationships that can provoke the teachers to refine pedagogical practices and deal with instructional issues. Action Cells are institutionalized by DepEd and offer formalized environments of collaborative professional development, where teachers have an opportunity to exchange best practices, analyze learner data, and discuss instructional issues collectively (Morales, 2023). All these supervisory practices are conducive to a positive

professional culture that appreciates collective teaching and learning.

The effectiveness of such practices according to research is constant in enhancing teacher competence and teaching. According to Sibomana (2020), the efficacy of teachers and classroom performance are enhanced significantly with the help of mentorship and structured feedback. However, difficulties remain. The passive involvement of teachers in professional learning, conflicted working hours, and lack of supervisory capacity of school heads limit the various effects of such practices. The barriers highlight the need to ensure that supervision systems are designed in ways that are responsive and sustainable according to the context.

The well-developed instructional supervisory practices play their roles in the enhancement of high-quality teaching and more encouraging learning conditions. Research has shown that regular feedback and coaching and professional development programs increase the instructional competence levels of teachers, confidence, and classroom management competencies, which, in turn, impact student achievement positively. Formal oversight also encourages the consistency between the instructional practices and the curriculum standards and the needs of learners (Kilag & Sasan, 2023). In addition to the personal growth of individual teachers, instructional supervision creates a culture of learning, accountability, and constant improvement in school. Maisyaroh et al. (2021) have found out that a school that has effective instructional leadership has a better level of collegiality and shared instructional responsibility.

Therefore, teaching supervision practices based on the country's policy and professional standards are important in enhancing the levels of teaching and learning in Philippine schools. Though legal frameworks offer a clear guideline on the instructional leadership role of the school heads, there are practical issues that still influence its implementation. There is therefore needed to strengthen the capacity of supervision by applying evidence-based interventions and context-based support mechanisms to maximize the effect of instructional supervision on teacher performance and school improvement (Montales & Digo, 2024).

Instructional supervision plays an imperative role in promoting the growth and performance of teachers, especially in the Philippine basic education system, where there have been constant issues concerning the lack of resources, different needs of learners, and different instructional capabilities that continue to influence the quality of teaching. School heads are key players in the process of influencing the instructions and practices by use of supervisory strategies that directly impact the professional competence, motivation, and effectiveness of teachers in the classroom. This discussion analyzes the

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impact of instructional supervisory practices on teacher performance and professional growth in terms of policy requirements, empirical research, and situational issues that influence supervisory efficacy.

The Philippines attach their practices of instructional supervision to the legal requirements established by the framework of school leadership and governance and the PPSSH institutionalized through the DepEd order No. 024, series of 2020. These policies also focus on instructional leadership as one of the major duties of school heads and present their involvement in teacher development and enhancing educational performance with the help of systematically guided and structured direction, control, and professional growth. School administrators have the authority to utilize instructional enhancements and to deliver professional growth opportunities that establish facilitating environments for excellent teaching and learning. The fact is supported by the evidence that the compliance with these legal norms has a positive impact on teacher performance. The study conducted by Aquino et al. (2021) indicates that school heads who have an active role in leadership, mentoring, and motivating teachers help to enhance the instructional practices and the results of the learners, which Culajara (2023) supports. On the other hand, poor leadership and supervision lead to stagnant instruction practices, which supports the requirement of clear legal and policy boundaries that will help to guide the effective instructional supervision.

Effective instructional supervision, grounded in strong management beliefs, promotes the professional development of teachers and enhances classroom practices. School heads who actively engage in coaching, mentoring, and performance feedback have a direct impact on teachers' skills and their classroom performance. These practices give teachers great opportunities to improve through regular feedback, guidance, and support, helping them enhance their teaching methods and overall instructional strategies.

Practically, instructional supervision is a performance support mechanism based on approaches to classroom observation, feedback systems, coaching cycles, instructional conferences, and applying structured observation tools. Classroom observations can regularly help school heads to understand what strengths and weaknesses in the instructional methods they use can be improved so that they can offer specific and positive feedback that helps a teacher develop further. Coaching cycles ensure the improvement process that is ongoing by assisting the teachers in setting objectives, analyzing the instruction practices, and modifying the pedagogical strategies. Salva et al. (2023) noted that such strategies can be more effective when school heads are trained to be able to provide feedback and coach effectively, which then enhances the motivation of the teachers and their self-efficacy (Arrieta, 2021). Nonetheless, the effectiveness of

supervisory support can be diminished by inconsistency in the feedback implementation and lack of clarity in performance expectations. As Diano and Calbi (2024) have noted, disjointed supervisory practice may confuse teachers and undermine the developmental effect of supervision, a point that Chin et al. (2022) also make.

Other than performance monitoring, instructional supervision has been used as a means of continuous professional development in the form of mentoring programs, LACs, Professional Learning Communities (PLCs), and reflective practices. Formal mentoring enables the novice teachers to gain the experience of their more accomplished peers, resulting in better classroom management, teaching planning, and interaction with the learners (Maisyaroh et al., 2021). The institutionalization of collaborative learning takes place in LACs, which promotes collaboration with their teachers to exchange best practices, discuss student data, and solve instructional challenges together (Morales, 2023). Research always shows that teachers become more confident, pedagogically competent, and better in delivery in a case when school heads give priority to professional learning initiatives (Zain et al., 2021). However, the efficiency of mentoring and teaming systems is determined by school culture, support of leadership, and quality of professional relations. Aquino et al. (2021) highlighted that school heads' and teachers' trust and collegiality are the important factors to evaluate the sustainability and effectiveness of the professional development program.

Although instructional supervision has potential benefits, several contextual conditions can reinforce or undermine its effect. The trust between the school heads and teachers is what enables the school heads to communicate and reflect with teachers in an open manner, where the teachers can consult and not fear they will be judged (Salva et al., 2023). Similarly, feedback can also be more welcome with the help of supervision that focuses on developmental growth instead of compliance and blame; thus, teachers will be more open to continuous improvement (Harries, 2024). On the other hand, too many workloads, administration pressures, and overly evaluative supervisory cultures can lead to stress and disengagement, thereby restricting the teacher's involvement in professional learning activities. Naparan and Tulod (2021) found that teachers who had a high workload demand showed signs of burnout, which adversely impacted performance and professional motivation. Such results support the necessity of balancing between accountability and professional support as well as proper time allocation to instructional leadership functions.

The practices implemented by school heads have significant implications for teacher performance and professional growth, especially when these are supported by legal mandates, effective supervisory practices, and a positive organizational environment. While existing policies

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provide clear guidelines for instructional leadership, the success of supervision largely depends on the consistent implementation of these policies, the leadership capabilities of school heads, and the presence of a supportive school culture. Therefore, there is a need to continuously improve supervisory practices and provide context-based interventions to enhance teacher competence and improve the overall quality of education in the Philippine basic education system.

Despite existing policies, there are still differences in how instructional supervision is carried out. School heads use different approaches, which results in unequal support and professional development opportunities for teachers across schools. This shows the need for a context-based training program that can give school heads clear and consistent guidance in instructional supervision. A well-designed learning and development program can strengthen instructional leadership, encourage the use of effective supervisory practices, and improve teachers' skills and professionalism. In the end, this can lead to better teaching practices and improved student learning outcomes.

Research supports the need for context-based intervention programs to standardize instructional practices in different school settings (Buban & Digo, 2021). These interventions help address the specific needs of each school while ensuring consistent quality in supervision and teacher development, which is important for improving teaching and learning. The legal background on the reinforced instructional supervision in the Philippines is based on the Republic Act No. 9155, which requires school heads to have instructional leadership and address accountability in school achievement. In addition to this requirement, the PPSSH defines leadership skills required to facilitate the improvement of instructional quality and teacher development. These policies set certain expectations according to which school leaders involve teachers in the perpetual professional learning, collaborative practice, and reflective improvement. These policy frameworks have been empirically proven to be effective in supervisory practice guidance. Culajara (2023) observed that leadership standards add positively to teacher efficacy and improvement of instruction. Nonetheless, research also shows a broad range between the translation of these policies into everyday supervisory behaviors, which make some teachers receive restricted instructional support and professional development. The conceptualized training design that can be made in accordance with these requirements can be used as a big help to standardize the processes of supervisors and can be adjusted to the situation in schools.

Evidence-based supervision models and instruments, including coaching models, systematized observation-feedback loops, and mentoring systems, are good consolidators of teacher performance and instructional

practices. Formal classroom observation can help school heads to collect data on instruction and give timely and specific feedback to promote reflection and growth of skills. Coaching models teach teamwork in solving problems and professional conversations to ensure that teachers perfect pedagogical techniques and enhance student interactions. The mentoring systems, especially among the novice teachers, foster professional confidence and instruction competence and facilitate innovative and reflective teaching practices (Maisyaroh et al., 2021). These models are highly effective, but they are not well employed because of lack of training, resources, and inconsistent supervisory ability by school leaders. This gap may be filled by proper training, which will explicitly describe procedures, tools, and best practices that can be used by school heads on a regular basis and in a productive way.

To create real impact, an instructional training program should have clear goals, simple and practical strategies, regular monitoring, and continuous training. Clear guidelines help school heads understand their roles better so they can carry out instructional supervision with confidence and consistency. The training should also be useful and easy to apply in real school situations so that school heads can use what they learn in their daily work (Sibomana, 2020). Regular monitoring helps leaders check if their strategies are working, identify problems, and keep improving their supervisory practices. Institutional leadership competencies of school heads are fortified by capacity-building elements, like training modules and reflective tools, as well as enhance the fidelity of implementation. These features guarantee that the conceptualized training design is not just a common seminar but also a dynamic resource of professional development and instructional enhancement.

The development of a conceptualized training design means that the contextual conditions should be taken into consideration with time allocation, the workload of teachers, leadership training, and the observance of supervisory protocols to be successful. The supervision and professional support activities are prioritized with the support of the 70/30 principle that prompts school heads to allocate more of their time to instructional leadership, as opposed to administrative work. It is also necessary to address the workload of teachers, since too many demands can restrict the participation in feedback, coaching, and professional learning programs. The ongoing training of school heads can guarantee the consistency of supervisory practices in response to the changes in instructional requirements and school demands, whereas long-term tracking guarantees consistency and responsibility (Zain et al., 2021; Harries, 2024). The proposed conceptualized instructional leadership training program will solve these concerns by providing viable steps to managing time, balancing workload, and planned professional support.

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The conceptualized training design can cover portions explaining the significance and purpose of instructional supervision; provide evidence-based supervision models and instruments, classroom observation, feedback, coaching, and mentoring procedures; and cover monitoring and evaluation processes. It can also offer resources for capacity building, modules of leadership, and approaches to fostering trust, cooperation, and open communication in schools. The benefit of such a structure is its perspective of the systematic implementation but also flexibility to adapt to the situation and ongoing enhancement.

To resolve the inconsistencies in supervisory practice, the school head in the Philippines can be provided with a context-based conceptualized instructional leadership training program that can be used as a practical intervention object that facilitates sustainable instructional change and leads to the improvement of the educational quality and performance of students.

This study, therefore, determined the instructional supervision practices employed by school heads and how these practices influence teacher performance and professional development. Specifically, it sought to identify the instructional supervisory practices currently used by school heads, determine how these supervisory practices influence and support the performance of teachers, and propose a training design that develops practical outputs for strengthening instructional supervision.

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design employed in the study was a descriptive qualitative research design, which is appropriate for exploring the instructional supervisory practices of school heads. This design allowed the researcher to gather non-numerical data in the form of interviews and narratives, providing deeper insights into the experiences and perceptions of participants within their actual school settings. Qualitative research is suitable when the goal is to examine meanings, experiences, and views, which is aligned with the Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) approach used in the data analysis (Byrne, 2021).

Reflexive thematic analysis was used to identify the main themes and patterns related to instructional supervision. The researcher applied an inductive approach, where the data were coded without using existing theories or frameworks, allowing the themes to emerge deeply and naturally from the participants' responses. This allowed the themes to emerge naturally from the participants' responses and experiences. The unstructured interviews also provided rich and detailed information about the participants' lived experiences regarding instructional supervision and its influence on teacher performance. Through RTA, the

researchers identified important themes connected to the participants' experiences and insights.

The RTA approach also encouraged continuous reflection throughout the analysis process. This helped the researcher identify patterns showing how supervisory practices affected teachers' professional growth and teaching effectiveness. At the same time, the researcher remained aware of personal perspectives while ensuring that the themes were still based on the actual responses of the participants. Overall, the thematic analysis provided clarity in terms of understanding supervisory practices and helped in developing an instructional leadership training design to strengthen the supervisory competencies of school heads.

Sources of Data

Purposive sampling was used in the selection of the participants of the study. Purposive sampling refers to the non-probability sampling method where the members are selected deliberately according to certain unique characteristics and experiences that are pertinent to the goals of the research. The strategy that was followed also made sure that only the people who had direct exposure to instructional supervision and at least some professional experiences were chosen.

The sample was composed of five elementary school principals, five head teachers, one teacher-in-charge, and five elementary teachers at the selected public elementary schools. School heads were chosen under the instructional supervisory position, whereas the teachers were chosen under the criteria of being under direct supervision of the participating school heads as well as having a minimum of two years of teaching experience within the same school. The composition enabled the study to elicit both the supervisory and instructional-level perspectives, which gave a clear picture about the instructional supervision in the district.

The participants, who served as data sources in the study, were 16 in total. Their responses gave the qualitative data that was required to respond to the research objectives and to establish the proposed instructional leadership training design.

Research Ethics

All ethical considerations were also strictly followed during the study conduct to safeguard the rights and well-being of every participant involved. Before data collection, the study subjects were given informed consent forms in which the objectives of the study, data collection methods, the threats and probable benefits of the research, and the rights of the subjects were outlined and explained clearly. It was voluntary participation, and the participants were made aware that they could pull out of the study at any given time with no adverse consequence.

Anonymity and confidentiality were provided through the coding of participants and elimination of any

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trace of identifying information in the interview transcripts and reports. All the data were stored safely and were seen by the researcher. To facilitate adherence to the set ethics, ethical permission was sought among the relevant authorities in the institution before the study was commenced.

Research Instrument

The main research tool to be employed in the given study was the interview guide, which was aimed at collecting qualitative data on the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and their impact on the performance of teachers. The interview guide was designed according to the research purposes and available literature on the topics of instructional supervision and leadership.

The interview guide used was in two forms, one being for school heads (principals, head teachers, and teachers in charge) and another being teachers. These two versions were open-ended questions arranged in three broad categories: instructional supervisory practices of school heads, the influence of instructional supervision on teacher performance and professional development, and inputs to the construction of an intervention or learning and development (L&D) proposal. The school head's questions were based on the strategies of supervision, adherence to DepEd policies, and the challenges that school heads had to deal with, as well as recommendations on how to improve the area of instructional leadership. At the same time, the teacher interview guide helped to extract the views of the teachers regarding the impact of supervision on their teaching practice, motivation, confidence, and professional development.

The interview guide also provided a short introduction section that explained the aim of the study, confidentiality, and how the participation was voluntary. Simple profiles like position, length of service, and level of education were also used to give background information on the responses. The respondents were permitted to use either English or Filipino so that they could feel comfortable and genuine when giving their experiences. All the interviews were held with informed consent, were recorded with permission, and were transcribed word-to-word to be analyzed further. In general, the interview guide was a useful qualitative tool that could be used to obtain abundant and descriptive accounts that could be used to identify the themes and formulate the proposed Learning and Development (L&D) proposal on instructional supervision.

Data Collection

The researcher adhered to the laid-down institutional and ethical procedures before data collection. A formal request to the Schools Division Office of Sorsogon to allow the conduct of the study. After the approval, the arranging of the interviews was coordinated with the public schools' district supervisors and the school heads.

The data were gathered using unstructured face-to-face interviews of the respondents. Informed consent was taken at the start of every interview, and the participants were informed of the confidentiality and the right to refuse. To be sure of accuracy and completeness of data, audio-recorded interviews were conducted.

The first objective of the study aimed to identify the instructional supervisory practices employed by school heads, including instructional monitoring, coaching, mentoring, and the facilitation of professional learning. The second objective sought to determine how these supervisory practices influence and support teachers' performance, as well as their professional development.

Following the initial analysis, a second round of interviews gathered participants' input on the proposed instructional leadership training design, focusing on its applicability, relevance, and feasibility within their school contexts. This consultation ensured that the training design was based on the actual needs and experiences of the participants. To further improve its relevance and implacability, the initial draft was reviewed by a university professor, refined by the researcher, and validated by three principals. Through this process an evidence-based, context-specific, and practical training design was developed to help strengthen the instructional supervision practices of school heads.

Data Analysis

The thematic analysis was used to examine the qualitative data, following the reflexive thematic analysis approach introduced by Braun and Clarke. The researchers first transcribed the recorded interviews word for word, to become more familiar with the data and gain a deeper understanding of the participants' responses. After carefully reviewing the transcripts, initial coding was conducted to identify significant pieces of information and ideas related to instructional supervision and performance of the teacher.

This process was carried out through six stages: familiarization with the data, generation of initial codes, theme search, theme review, theme definition, and final report production. The first objective focused on identifying themes related to the common instructional supervisory practices of school heads. The second objective examined themes centered on the influence of these practices on teacher performance and professional development. For the third objective, the post-intervention interview responses were analyzed to identify themes related to the relevance, strengths, and areas for improvement of the proposed instructional leadership training design.

To ensure the analytical rigor of this study, the artificial intelligence tool ChatGPT by OpenAI was used during the initial stages for the analysis of data to assist in organizing codes and clustering similar ideas. The AI-assisted outputs were carefully reviewed, validated, and

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refined by the researcher to ensure accuracy, relevance, and academic integrity. The combination of the researcher’s expertise and AI support helped strengthen the credibility and validity of the thematic analysis while preserving the authenticity of the participants’ responses.

III. RESULTS

The interview results show the important role of school heads in instructional supervision. Participants explained that school heads are essential in guiding, supporting, and monitoring teachers to improve teaching and learning in school settings. These insights provided a clearer understanding of how supervision is practiced in real school settings. In addition, the findings served as the basis for

developing the proposed intervention program aimed at strengthening instructional leadership and improving supervisory practices.

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Heads

The discussion below provides an overview of the instructional supervisory practices of school heads. It is based on the experiences shared by the participants and is further supported by related literature. Given these practices, the researcher determined the role played by leadership strategies of school heads in enhancing performance of teachers and overall quality of education in the schools where they serve. Table 1 shows these themes.

Table 1. Instructional Monitoring and Policy Adherence

Subthemes	Description	Evidence / Narratives
1.1: Standardized Classroom Observation and Evaluation Data-Driven and Policy-Aligned Supervision	<p>School heads employ structured classroom observation processes such as pre-conferences, actual observations, and post-conferences to assess teaching practices and guide improvement.</p> <p>Instructional monitoring has evolved into a data-driven process that enables school heads to make informed and objective decisions.</p>	<p>“Kadalasan, ginagamit ko ang clinical supervision bilang pangunahing instructional strategy... Bago pa man magsagawa ng obserbasyon, nagkakaroon muna kami ng pre-conference upang pag-usapan ang mga layunin at mga aspeto na dapat pagtuunan ng pansin.” - Principal 4</p> <p>“I consistently refer to the RPMS-PPST, MELCs, and other DepEd issuances as the foundation for planning instructional activities and guiding teachers in improving their classroom practices.” - Principal 3</p> <p>“Ang data-driven process ay nagagamit ko din sa pag-supervise ko sa mga teachers na hawak ko... sinusuri ko ang kanilang mga outputs at ang learning outcomes ng mga bata upang matiyak na ang bawat guro ay nakapagtuturo nang naaayon sa pamantayan at layunin ng kurikulum.” – Head Teacher 1</p>
1.2. Compliance and Instructional Quality Assurance	<p>Another critical dimension of instructional monitoring is ensuring compliance with prescribed standards through the review of instructional materials and records. This includes checking Daily Lesson Logs (DLLs), Detailed Lesson Plans (DLPs), and other teaching resources.</p>	<p>“Regular kong tinitingnan ang kanilang mga lesson plans at iba pang instructional materials upang masiguro na ito ay angkop sa pangangailangan ng mga bata at sumusunod sa itinakdang curriculum.” – Principal 5</p> <p>“The monitoring and evaluation of programs... ensure that teachers are on the right track in their teaching journey.” - Principal 1</p>

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Individualized Coaching, Mentoring, and Technical Assistance

This theme reflects a paradigm shift from inspection-based supervision toward a more developmental and collaborative “partnership” model. Recent studies support this shift by showing that continuous and job-embedded professional development, such as coaching and mentoring, gives great improvement for teachers’ competence, confidence, and overall quality of instruction.

The succeeding table also presents the responses of the participants regarding the importance of coaching, mentoring, and technical assistance as key parts of instructional supervision. Although instructional monitoring helps identify gaps and areas that need improvement, the participants emphasized that teachers also need individualized guidance and professional support to address instructional challenges effectively. These findings show a shift from the traditional supervision approach that focused mainly on inspection toward a more collaborative and developmental process that encourages professional growth,

Facilitation of Collective Professional Learning

This theme highlights the important role of school heads as “lead learners” who promote a culture of shared learning and continuous professional development among teachers. Instead of focusing only on individual teacher improvement, this approach encourages collective learning as an effective way to strengthen instructional practices and improve overall school performance.

Table 3 presents the participants’ responses regarding the facilitation of collective professional learning as an important instructional supervisory practice of school heads. The findings highlight how collaborative learning activities such as Learning Action Cells (LAC), peer sharing, mentoring sessions, and professional discussions contribute to teachers’ professional growth and instructional improvement. Participants emphasized that collective professional learning fosters collaboration, reflective practice, knowledge sharing, and continuous capacity building among teachers, ultimately enhancing the quality of teaching and learning in schools.

Table 2. Individualized Coaching, Mentoring, and Technical Assistance

Subthemes	Description	Evidence/Narrative
2.1 One-on-one mentoring sessions and Targeted Feedback	Technical assistance becomes most effective when framed as supportive rather than corrective.	<p><i>"Lahat ng feedback ay para dapat sa pagtulong, hindi para manita." – Head Teacher 2</i></p> <p><i>"Hindi naman siya agad nagbibigay ng puna, kundi nagtatanong muna... Maganda ito kasi nagkakaroon ng reflective discussion." - Teacher1</i></p> <p><i>"Ang feedback ng aming school head ay itinuturing kong oportunidad upang matuto... ginagawa ko itong inspirasyon."- Teacher 4</i></p> <p><i>"Mas kumportable kasi minsan ang mga guro kapag kapwa nila guro ang kanilang kasama sa pagtukoy ng kanilang kahinaan." - Principal 1</i></p> <p><i>"Mga mas bihasa at bagong guro upang magkaroon ng tuloy-tuloy na gabay." - Heat Teacher 3</i></p> <p><i>"Para sa mga newly hired teachers dapat mabigyan sila ng sapat na gabay sa pagplaplano ng kanilang susunod na aralin." - Principal 4</i></p> <p><i>"Humihingi ako ng follow-up guidance sa aking school head upang malaman kung tama ang aking mga naging hakbang." - Teacher 3</i></p>
2.2: Collaborative Mentorship and Peer Support Systems	Strengthen a culture of collaboration and continuous learning within the school.	

instructional improvement, and continuous learning among teachers

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Table 3. Facilitation of Collective Professional Learning

Subthemes	Description	Evidence/Narrative
3.1. Sustaining Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions	School principals, head teachers, and TICs utilize structured platforms such as Learning Action Cells (LACs) to promote collaborative planning, best practice sharing, and discussion of instructional challenges.	"Mas klarado at malinaw naming napag-uusapan ang dapat topic na napapanahon. ang ganitong estratehiya ay proven at tested na." - Principal 4 "Lumalalim ang kaalaman ng mga guro at nagiging mas ko epektibo ang kanilang kaalaman sa pagtuturo." - Head Teacher 2
3.2. Capacity Building through INSET, Workshops, and Wellness	These initiatives address not only the technical needs of teachers but also their overall professional growth, helping ensure that professional development remains meaningful, well-rounded, and sustainable.	"Train at ma refresh ang mga guro... nakatuon sa mga makabagong pamamaraan tulad ng multimedia." - Principal 5 "Napapa unlad kasi ang aming kaalaman sa ganitong set up, napaka importante ng INSET." - Teacher 5

Influence of Instructional Supervision on Teacher Performance and Professional Growth

Tables 4 and 5 present the major themes identified from the data on how instructional supervisory practices support teacher performance and professional growth. The analysis of the interview responses revealed several supervisory practices

that play an important role in promoting teacher development, improving instructional quality, and enhancing classroom performance.

Table 4. Influence of Instructional Supervisory Practices on Teacher Performance

Subthemes	Description	Evidence / Narratives
1.1. Feedback and Coaching for Professional Growth	School heads provided personalized feedback and coaching to help teachers improve their instructional strategies and performance.	"Ginagawa kong konkretong aksyon ang kanyang mga rekomendasyon, tulad ng pag-revise ng lesson plan o paggamit ng mas angkop na teaching strategy." - Teacher 2
1.2. Mentorship for New and Struggling Teachers	Mentorship programs were used to guide new or struggling teachers by providing them with advice, support, and resources for improvement.	"Ang mentorship ay nakatutulong lalo na sa mga bagong guro... sa tulong ng mga guro na mas marurunong, mas gumaling sila sa loob ng silid-aralan." - Principal 3
1.3. Reflective Practices and Continuous Monitoring	Regular follow-up and reflective practices were used to monitor teachers' progress and ensure the implementation of feedback.	"Bumabalik siya pagkatapos ng ilang araw para tingnan kung naipatupad ko ba ang mga suggestions niya." -Teacher 5
1.4. Data-Driven Instructional Support	Data-driven approaches were used to target specific areas for improvement, ensuring that interventions were effective and relevant.	"Ang data-driven process ay nagagamit ko din sa pag supervise ko sa mga teachers na hawak ko...nagkakaroon kami ng konkretong batayan sa pagbibigay ng feedback." - Head Teacher 3

Table 5. Influence of Instructional Supervisory Practices on Teacher Professional Growth

Themes	Description	Evidence / Narratives
2.1. Collaborative Learning and Sharing Best Practices	Teachers participated in Learning Action Cells (LAC), peer coaching, and team teaching to share best practices and address challenges collaboratively.	<i>“Sa LAC, nagkakaroon kami ng pagkakataon na magbahagi ng best practices at mga challenges sa pagtuturo.” - Teacher 4</i>
2.2. Supportive School Culture	A non-threatening and supportive school culture was cultivated to help teachers feel safe in trying new approaches and enhancing their skills.	<i>“Ang pinakamalaking tulong o suportang ibinibigay namin ay ang kulturang kung saan ligtas ang pakiramdam ng mga guro na sumubok ng bagong bagay at mag-develop.” – Head Teacher 5</i>

IV. DISCUSSION

This section presents the key findings of the study, particularly the instructional supervisory practices of school heads and their influence on teacher performance. It discusses how supervision supports teachers professionally, improves instructional practices, and encourages reflective teaching through different leadership styles. This discussion also focused on the importance of evidence-based and collaborative approaches in strengthening the quality of teaching strategies in school.

Instructional Leadership Practices of School Heads

The study emphasized that the effectiveness of school heads in improving teaching quality is strongly anchored in their instructional supervisory practices. These practices include structured classroom observation, individualized coaching and mentoring, support for professional learning, and data-based instructional assistance. Instructional monitoring was engaged as one of the key supervisory practices, where school heads conducted pre-conferences, classroom observations, and post-conferences to assess teaching performance, identify areas for improvement, and provide constructive feedback. Through this systematic process, supervision was not only used for evaluation but also for professional development. It helped teachers improve their practice while ensuring alignment with national standards such as RPMS-PPST and MELCs.

Alongside classroom observation, the study found that data-driven instructional support is another important supervisory practice. School heads use student performance data, classroom observation results, and teacher evaluations to give clear and targeted guidance to teachers.

This approach enabled them to identify individual teacher needs as well as common instructional concerns within the school. As a result, the feedback and coaching given were more relevant, timely, and better suited to

teachers’ professional needs. By relying on measurable evidence rather than personal judgment, school heads were able to offer personalized and practical support that strengthened teacher competence and improved instructional quality (Kilag & Sasan, 2023)

In the same way, data-driven supervision helps address immediate teaching concerns while improving overall teaching quality. Performance reports and student assessment results are used as the basis for clear and practical feedback after classroom observations (Tan et al., 2021). This kind of objective feedback also promotes fairness among teachers, reduces misunderstandings, and helps teachers focus on improving specific teaching practices.

Despite its advantages, the study also revealed several challenges in implementing data-driven instructional support. These included limited time for data analysis and inconsistencies in the quality of available information. However, the use of data is still aligned with best practices in instructional leadership, where information is used to guide supervision and improve teaching and learning outcomes (Pomental, 2024). Using data effectively helps school heads give focused support, track teacher progress, and adjust teaching strategies to meet the needs of learners. These findings highlight the importance of strengthening information systems and providing training opportunities to maximize the effectiveness of instructional supervision.

In addition to data-driven support, coaching and mentoring also play an important role in improving teachers’ professional growth. These practices provided individualized guidance tailored to the needs of teachers, especially those who were beginning in the profession or experiencing instructional difficulties. Peer coaching and collaborative reflection help build trust, reduce anxiety about supervision, and encourage teachers to learn from one another. In addition, timely and constructive feedback, along with follow-up observations, allows teachers to apply

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suggestions and reflect more deeply on their teaching practices.

Professional learning facilitation further expanded the supervisory role of school heads by creating collaborative learning opportunities within the school. Through activities such as Learning Action Cells (LACs), teachers were given opportunities to share their experiences, discuss challenges, and work together in developing strategies to improve instruction. These practices support teacher empowerment, continuous professional growth, and a culture of teamwork and ongoing improvement within the school community.

Overall, the instructional supervisory practices of school heads reflect the integration of structured observation, coaching and mentoring, collaborative professional learning, and data-informed support. Collectively, these practices help improve teacher competence, enhance instructional quality, and support continuous professional growth. More importantly, they show that effective instructional supervision is organized, based on evidence, and responsive to the different needs of teachers (Kilag & Sasan, 2023; Tan et al., 2021; Pomentel, 2024).

a. Instructional Monitoring and Policy Adherence.

Instructional monitoring in the schools included in the study serves as a primary mechanism for maintaining the quality of classroom instruction. It ensures that teaching practices are not only effective but also aligned with the national educational standards and the requirements of the Department of Education in the Philippines.

This theme highlights the important role of school heads as “guardians of quality,” whose responsibility is to ensure that classroom practices are consistent with the broader goals and expectations of the education system. Instructional monitoring is not done occasionally or informally. Instead, it is a structured and organized process that connects educational policies with what happens in the classroom.

Supporting this finding, some recent studies emphasize that strong instructional leadership, particularly through consistent monitoring and alignment with standards, has a positive impact on teaching quality and student achievement. Hallinger et al. (2018) noted that school leadership practices focused on instructional supervision and policy alignment are strongly linked to improved school performance. This supports the present study’s findings that instructional monitoring plays a vital role in maintaining consistency, accountability, and quality in classroom instruction across schools.

b. Standardized Classroom Observation and Evaluation.

The data revealed that school heads commonly use a clinical supervision model characterized by a structured and transparent evaluation process. This process includes three important phases: pre-observation, classroom observation,

and post-observation feedback. Principal 4 explained this systematic approach by stating, “*mas gamay ko ang clinical supervision... Bago ako mag-observe, pre-conference muna, then post-conference upang ibigay ang feedback at pag-usapan ang mga paraan para lalong mapabuti ang pagtuturo.*” This practice shows that classroom observations are not intended solely for evaluation or fault-finding but rather as part of an ongoing process of professional improvement. Through this structured approach, school heads and teachers develop clearer communication, mutual understanding, and shared responsibility in improving the teaching and learning process.

Moreover, instructional supervision is strongly anchored on national standards rather than on personal judgment or subjective opinions. Principal 3 emphasized this alignment by stating, “I consistently refer to the RPMS-PPST, MELCs, and other DepEd issuances as the foundation for planning instructional activities and guiding teachers in improving their classroom practices.” By using the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) as a guide, school heads ensure that instructional quality is assessed using a nationally recognized framework. This approach promotes fairness, consistency, and accountability in the supervision process across schools.

Recent empirical studies further support the effectiveness of structured observation systems in improving teaching practices. Gärtner (2017) found that standardized classroom observations significantly enhance teaching quality when combined with constructive feedback and reflective discussions. In the same way, Bell et al. (2019) emphasized that observation-based evaluation systems become more effective when they are transparent, criteria-based, and connected to professional development opportunities for teachers. These studies affirm the importance of systematic supervision practices in promoting instructional improvement and teacher growth.

The findings of the present study also reinforce the enduring relevance of the Clinical Supervision Theory of Morris L. Goldhammer (1969), which highlights systematic classroom observation and reflective dialogue as essential components of teacher improvement. In the Philippine educational context, this approach is further strengthened through DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, which institutionalizes the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) as the basis for performance management. Through this policy, instructional quality is clearly defined and consistently applied, guiding school heads in carrying out effective and standards-based instructional supervision.

c. Data-Driven and Policy-Aligned Supervision. Beyond direct classroom observation, instructional monitoring has evolved into a more data-driven process that enables school heads to make informed and objective decisions regarding instruction. School leaders now increasingly rely on empirical evidence to identify instructional gaps and

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determine the most appropriate interventions to support teachers and improve student learning outcomes.

This practice was clearly said by Head Teacher 1, who stated, "*Ang data-driven yun ang epektibo para sa kin, kasi mas tangible ang data, mas madali ang pag TA sa guro*" ("Data-driven approaches are more effective because the data are more tangible, making technical assistance easier to teachers"). In the same way, Head Teacher 4 highlighted the importance of assessment results by explaining, "*Sinusuri namin ang resulta ng mga assessments ng mga mag-aaral upang matukoy kung anong bahagi kailangang paunlarin at kung anong suporta ang dapat ibigay sa guro*" ("We analyze the results of learners' assessments to point out which aspects of instruction need improvement and what support should be provided to the teacher."). These responses show a shift from subjective judgment toward evidence-based supervision. By examining student performance data and teacher outputs, school heads are better able to identify specific instructional concerns and provide targeted support to teachers.

The other studies strongly support the effectiveness of this approach. Datnow and Park (2018) found that data-driven decision-making improves instructional alignment and student achievement when school leaders actively involve teachers in the interpretation and use of data. Similarly, Poortman and Schildkamp (2016) revealed that schools that systematically utilize data in instructional decision-making gives higher levels of teacher collaboration and instructional effectiveness. These findings suggest that the strategic use of data not only improves teaching practices but also improves collaborative learning among educators.

The findings of the present study also align with the earlier work of Kim Schildkamp and Melanie Ehren (2013), whose research highlighted that data-informed supervision promotes more objective feedback, stronger accountability, and improved learning outcomes. Their work continues to be supported by recent studies highlighting the importance of evidence-based supervision in educational leadership.

Furthermore, the implementation of DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, or the Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment, ensures that the data used in instructional supervision are aligned with national educational standards. This policy reinforces the importance of learner outcomes as a central basis for monitoring instruction and guiding teachers toward continuous improvement in classroom practice.

d. Compliance and Instructional Quality Assurance.

Another critical dimension of instructional monitoring is ensuring compliance with DepEd standards through the regular review of instructional materials and teaching records. This process includes checking Daily Lesson Logs (DLLs), Detailed Lesson Plans (DLPs), and other

instructional resources used by teachers. Principal 5 emphasized the importance of this responsibility by stating, "*Palagi kong tsene-check ang kanilang mga lesson plans at iba pang instructional materials upang masiguro na ito ay naka base sa MELCs at sa need ng mga bata na matutunan*" ("I regularly review their lesson plans and other instructional materials to ensure that these are appropriate to the needs of the learners and aligned with the prescribed curriculum"). Through this practice, school leaders ensure that teachers are well-prepared and that the intended curriculum is properly implemented in the classroom. At the same time, it helps align instructional delivery with the national learning competencies set by the Department of Education.

In addition, Principal 1 highlighted the importance of monitoring in maintaining instructional direction by stating, "The monitoring and evaluation of programs... ensure that teachers are on the right track in their teaching journey." This form of compliance-oriented supervision serves as a safeguard against instructional inconsistency, particularly within decentralized educational systems. It ensures that teachers, regardless of their school location, follow the same standards, curriculum goals, and instructional expectations. As a result, instructional supervision promotes consistency and accountability in the delivery of quality education.

Some studies support the importance of balancing accountability with instructional support. Tuytens and Devos (2017) found that teacher evaluation systems that integrate accountability measures with developmental support contribute to improved teacher performance and stronger professional commitment. Likewise, reports from the OECD (2020) emphasize that effective educational systems maintain strong quality assurance mechanisms while also encouraging teacher autonomy and professional growth. These findings suggest that supervision becomes more effective when it not only monitors compliance but also supports teachers in improving their instructional practices.

The findings of the present study also reflect the earlier work of Don Beach and James Reinehart (1989), who argued that instructional supervision should include a quality control component to ensure that school goals are achieved through proper curriculum implementation. Their perspective reinforces the idea that monitoring is essential in maintaining alignment between educational policies and actual classroom practices.

Overall, Theme 1 highlights that instructional monitoring is a multifaceted process that combines structured observation, data-driven decision-making, and compliance checking to ensure instructional quality and alignment with educational policies. Recent empirical studies from 2015 to 2025 consistently support the effectiveness of these practices. Structured and standards-based classroom observations improve teaching quality

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(Gärtner, 2017; Bell et al., 2019), while data-driven supervision enhances instructional decision-making and student learning outcomes (Datnow & Park, 2018; Poortman & Schildkamp, 2016). Furthermore, balanced systems that integrate accountability and professional support strengthen teacher performance and commitment (Tuytens & Devos, 2017; OECD, 2020). These findings, together with the experiences shared by the participants, demonstrate that effective instructional monitoring goes beyond ensuring compliance and instead promotes coherence between educational policy and classroom practice.

Ultimately, the role of the school head as a “guardian of quality” remains essential in maintaining high standards of teaching and learning. Through structured supervision, evidence-based decision-making, and adherence to educational policies, school leaders help create a system where instructional practices remain aligned with national goals. In doing so, they contribute to the delivery of equitable, consistent, and high-quality education for all learners.

2. Individualized Coaching, Mentoring, and Technical Assistance. While instructional monitoring helps identify instructional gaps and areas that need improvement, these concerns are more effectively addressed through coaching, mentoring, and technical assistance. This theme reflects a shift from the traditional inspection-based style of supervision toward a more supportive and collaborative approach. Rather than focusing only on evaluation, supervision now gives importance to guidance, encouragement, and professional support that help teachers improve their instructional practices. Through this approach, school heads serve not only as evaluators but also as partners in teachers’ professional growth.

Recent studies strongly support this transition, showing that continuous and job-embedded professional development, especially coaching and mentoring, positively influences teachers’ competence, confidence, and instructional quality. A systematic review by Ramadhona et al. (2025) found that instructional coaching helps improve teachers’ professional growth by making them more open to feedback and strengthening their teaching practices. This supports the findings of the present study, which showed that coaching becomes more effective when it is personalized, supportive, and built on trust and collaboration rather than focused mainly on evaluation.

a. Provision of Technical Assistance (TA) and Targeted Feedback. The findings highlight that technical assistance (TA) becomes more effective when it is delivered in a supportive rather than corrective manner. School heads intentionally shift the focus of feedback from fault-finding to professional growth and improvement. This is reflected in the statement of Head Teacher 2: “*Lahat ng feedback ay para dapat nakakatulong sa guro, hindi para manita*” (“All feedback should be intended to help, not to criticize.”). This

approach creates a more positive and encouraging environment where teachers feel supported rather than judged. There are studies that show that coaching environments built on trust and psychological safety improve teachers’ engagement and openness to feedback. When teachers look feedback as developmental instead of evaluative, they become more willing to reflect on their teaching practices and apply improvements in the classroom.

In addition, the use of reflective questioning emerged as an important feedback strategy. Teacher 1 shared, “*Hindi naman siya agad nagbibigay ng puna, kundi nagtatanong muna... Maganda ito kasi nagkakaroon kami reflective discussion, nakakatulong talaga*” (“They do not immediately give criticism but instead ask questions first... It really helped me... This is good because it leads to reflective discussions”). This practice encourages teachers to reflect on their own instructional practices and identify areas for improvement through meaningful dialogue. Research also supports this approach, showing that coaching and mentoring become more effective when they involve reflective discussions rather than purely directive feedback. Studies indicate that reflective coaching strategies help improve teachers’ instructional clarity and lesson planning skills.

Furthermore, Teacher 4 emphasized the motivational effect of constructive feedback by stating, “*Ang feedback ng aming school head ay itinuturing kong oportunidad upang matuto... ginagawa ko itong inspirasyon, hindi sagabal*” (“I consider the feedback from our school head as an opportunity to learn... I use it as an inspiration and not a hindrance”). This finding suggests that supportive feedback not only improves instructional practices but also strengthens teacher motivation and confidence. Empirical studies support this idea, showing that effective coaching enhances teachers’ self-efficacy and willingness to adopt new teaching strategies, which are important for continuous instructional improvement.

These findings are consistent with the Partnership Principles of Jim Knight (2007), which emphasize dialogue, reflection, and equality in instructional coaching. When feedback becomes a collaborative process rather than a top-down directive, teachers are encouraged to take ownership of their professional learning. As a result, supervision becomes more meaningful and contributes to deeper and more sustainable professional growth.

b. Collaborative Mentorship and Peer Support Systems. In addition to individualized coaching, the study also highlights the importance of collaborative mentorship and peer support systems in improving teachers’ professional practices. Teachers often feel more comfortable learning and sharing experiences with fellow teachers, as reflected in the statement of Principal 1: “*Mas gusto kasi minsan ang mga guro kapag kapwa nila guro ang kanilang kasama sa pagtukoy ng kanilang strenght and weakness*” (“Teachers

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sometimes feel more comfortable when fellow teachers help them point out their areas for improvement"). This finding is supported by some studies showing that peer coaching creates a less threatening environment that encourages openness, willingness for collaboration, and reflective practice among teachers.

To strengthen this practice, school heads implement structured mentoring systems within the school. Principal 4 shared that he pairs "*nakakatulong din ang mga Master Teachers sa pag bigay ng TA, mas matututukan sila*" ("more experienced teachers with newly hired teachers to provide continuous guidance"). In the same way, Head Teacher 3 emphasized the need for targeted support for beginning teachers by stating, "*para sa mga newly hired teachers naman, dapat talaga sila ay may sapat na gabay sa pagplaplano ng kanilang susunod na aralin*" ("Newly hired teachers should be given enough guidance in planning their succeeding lessons"). These practices show the important role of mentoring in helping novice teachers adjust to classroom demands and improve their instructional skills.

Recent empirical evidence in the Philippine context further supports the effectiveness of peer coaching and mentoring. A study by Lualhati and Karanjakwut (2025) found that peer coaching significantly improves lesson planning, instructional delivery, and reflective practices among teachers. The study also revealed a positive relationship between peer coaching and academic performance, emphasizing that structured peer support strengthens teaching competencies and promotes continuous professional learning.

Moreover, Teacher 3's statement talks about the sustained nature of mentoring and professional guidance: "*hindi ako nahihyang magtanong sa aking school head para sa guidance, upang malaman kung tama ang aking mga naging hakbang*" ("I seek follow-up guidance from my school head to know whether the steps I have taken are aligned"). This response emphasizes the importance of continuous support rather than short interventions. Research consistently shows that ongoing coaching and mentoring are necessary to ensure that professional development is effectively translated into actual classroom practice. Without sustained follow-up, the application of new learning and teaching strategies may become limited.

The findings also reinforce the earlier work of Bruce Joyce and Beverly Showers (2002), whose studies showed that peer coaching increases the likelihood that teachers will effectively apply new teaching strategies in the classroom. Their work continues to be supported by recent studies emphasizing the value of collaborative learning and continuous guidance in teacher development.

Overall, Theme 2 demonstrates that effective instructional supervision is grounded in sustained, personalized, and collaborative support systems. Coaching, mentoring, and technical assistance serve as important

mechanisms that connect evaluation with actual improvement in teaching practices. Recent empirical studies consistently affirm that instructional coaching improves teacher confidence, openness to feedback, and professional growth, while reflective and dialogic feedback strengthens instructional clarity and lesson planning. Likewise, peer coaching promotes better instructional delivery, reflective practice, and collaborative learning cultures within schools.

The integration of these findings with the lived experiences of the participants presents a clear picture that teachers thrive in environments where supervision is supportive, collaborative, and responsive to their needs. The shift toward a partnership model of supervision transforms instructional leadership into a more relational and growth-oriented process. By fostering trust, open communication, and shared responsibility, school heads not only improve teacher competence but also help build a culture of continuous improvement that contributes to better teaching practices and improved student learning outcomes.

3. Facilitation of Collective Professional Learning

This theme highlights the very important role of the school head as a "lead learner" who gives a culture of shared growth and continuous professional development among teachers. Rather than focusing only on individual improvement, this approach emphasizes collective learning as a powerful strategy of school-wide instructional enhancement. In this model, professional development is not isolated but anchored within collaborative structures that allow teachers to learn, reflect, share one another's experiences, and co-construct knowledge.

Studies affirm that collective professional learning, particularly when it is sustained, collaborative, and context-specific, has an important impact on instructional quality and student outcomes. For instance, a meta-analysis by Matthew A. Kraft et al. (2018) highlights that professional learning models involving collaboration and coaching yield stronger improvements in teaching strategies compared to traditional, one-day training sessions. This underscores the importance of structured, school-based learning opportunities such as LAC sessions and INSET programs.

a. Sustaining Learning Action Cell (LAC) Sessions. The Learning Action Cell (LAC) emerged as a central mechanism for facilitating collective professional learning within the school. Participants consistently identified LAC sessions as a vital platform for knowledge sharing, collaborative problem-solving, and reflective practice. Principal 2 described LAC as a venue where "*mas malinaw at maayos na natatalakay ang mga bagay na nais malaman... Proven ang ganitong estratehiya.*" ("The matters they want to understand are discussed more clearly and effectively... This kind of strategy has already been proven effective.") This highlights the structured and purposeful nature of LAC sessions in addressing teachers' professional needs.

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Similarly, Head Teacher 2 emphasized the collaborative benefits of LAC, stating that *"lumalalim ang kaalaman ng mga guro at nagiging mas kolaboratibo ang kapaligiran"* ("Teachers' knowledge deepens, and the environment becomes more collaborative"). These sessions create opportunities for teachers to exchange "best practices," discuss instructional challenges, and co-develop solutions grounded in their shared classroom realities. This finding aligns strongly with the policy framework of the Department of Education (Philippines) under DepEd Order No. 35, s. 2016, which institutionalized LAC as a primary strategy for school-based professional development. The policy recognizes that teachers learn most effectively from peers within their own context, making LAC a sustainable and relevant approach to capacity building.

Recent research further supports the effectiveness of professional learning communities (PLCs) like LAC. Studies conducted between 2016 and 2023 indicate that structured collaborative learning groups significantly enhance teacher knowledge, instructional practices, and student achievement. For example, Vangrieken et al. (2017) found that collaboration among teachers fosters deeper professional engagement and shared responsibility for student learning. Additionally, Tan et al. (2022) reported that school-based professional learning communities improve teachers' reflective practices and instructional decision-making.

Thus, LAC sessions function not only as venues for discussion but as dynamic spaces for professional transformation, reinforcing the idea that collective learning is a cornerstone of effective instructional leadership.

Capacity Building through INSET, Workshops, and Wellness. Beyond LAC sessions, the study reveals that school heads facilitate professional growth through structured capacity-building initiatives such as INSET (In-Service Training), workshops, and wellness programs. These initiatives address both the technical and holistic needs of teachers, ensuring that professional development is comprehensive and sustainable.

Principal 5 highlighted the role of INSET in updating teachers' competencies, stating that it is used to *"train at ma refresh ang mga guro... nakatuon sa mga makabagong pamamaraan tulad ng multimedia"* ("Teachers are trained and refreshed... focusing on modern approaches such as the use of multimedia"). This reflects the increasing emphasis on integrating 21st-century skills and digital competencies into teaching practices, which is supported by recent studies showing that technology-focused professional development enhances instructional effectiveness and student engagement.

At the same time, school leaders recognize that teacher performance is closely linked to well-being. Principal 4 emphasized the importance of support systems by providing "wellness workshops, access to a counselor,

and an open-door policy." This holistic approach acknowledges the emotional and psychological demands of teaching, particularly in high-pressure environments. Teacher 5 affirmed the practical impact of these capacity-building efforts, stating, *"Tinitiyak kong subukan ko ito at inoobserbahan kung epektibo sa aking mga mag-aaral."* ("I make sure to apply it and observe whether it is effective for my learners.") This reflects an important outcome of effective professional development; teachers not only acquire new knowledge but also apply and evaluate it in their classroom contexts.

Recent empirical studies reinforce the importance of combining technical training with well-being initiatives. Research by Collie (2021) found that teacher well-being is strongly associated with job satisfaction, instructional quality, and student outcomes. Similarly, a study by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) emphasized that effective professional development must be sustained, collaborative, and responsive to teachers' needs, including their emotional well-being.

These findings are consistent with the work of Christopher Day and Qing Gu (2010), who argued that teacher resilience and professional well-being are essential for maintaining long-term instructional effectiveness. Their work, although earlier, continues to be validated by recent research emphasizing the need for holistic teacher support systems.

Theme 3 underscores that effective instructional leadership extends beyond individual supervision and into the cultivation of a collaborative learning culture within the school. By sustaining LAC sessions and implementing comprehensive capacity-building initiatives, school heads create structured opportunities for teachers to grow collectively. Recent empirical evidence consistently highlights that collaborative professional learning communities improve instructional practices and teacher engagement (Vangrieken et al., 2017; Tan et al., 2022). Sustained and context-based professional development is more effective than one-time training (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017; Matthew A. Kraft et al., 2018). Teacher well-being significantly influences instructional quality and professional commitment (Collie, 2021).

The integration of these findings with participants' experiences demonstrates that collective professional learning is both practical and transformative. Teachers benefit not only from acquiring new knowledge but also from engaging in meaningful collaboration and receiving holistic support. The role of the school head as a "Lead Learner" is crucial in sustaining a culture of continuous improvement. By balancing technical training, collaborative learning, and teacher well-being, school leaders ensure that professional development is not only effective but also sustainable, leading to improved teaching practices and enhanced student learning outcomes.

The Influence of Instructional Supervisory Practices on Teacher Performance and Support

The study revealed that instructional supervision significantly supports teacher performance by fostering professional growth, enhancing instructional competence, and improving classroom practices. A central mechanism through which supervision impacts teachers is reflective practice, which enables educators to critically examine their teaching methods, classroom management strategies, and lesson delivery. School heads emphasized reflection as an integral part of their supervisory routines, encouraging teachers to self-assess and take ownership of their professional development. Through structured post-observation conferences, teachers were invited to share experiences, discuss challenges, and evaluate their own instructional practices. This two-way communication not only promoted accountability but also cultivated teacher autonomy, allowing educators to actively engage in improving their teaching (Sibomana, 2020; Maisyaroh et al., 2021).

Reflective practices also contributed to the development of teacher confidence and motivation. By recognizing their strengths and identifying areas for improvement, teachers became more aware of their professional growth, which fostered a positive disposition toward continuous improvement. Structured reflection empowered teachers to implement evidence-based changes in their instructional strategies and to monitor their own progress over time. Research indicates that opportunities for systematic reflection are strongly associated with sustained professional development, as teachers are more likely to embrace ongoing learning when reflection is framed as a developmental rather than evaluative process.

Another significant aspect of supervision that influences teacher performance is the integration of data-driven instructional support. School heads utilized student performance metrics, classroom observation records, and teacher evaluation data to provide personalized feedback. This evidence-based approach allowed supervisors to target specific areas of improvement, offer actionable guidance, and ensure that interventions were relevant and practical. Teachers receiving data-informed feedback were able to implement precise instructional adjustments, thereby enhancing classroom effectiveness and instructional quality (Kilag & Sasan, 2023; Tan et al., 2021; Pomentel, 2024). The study also highlighted the importance of a supportive and collaborative school culture in maximizing the effectiveness of instructional supervision. Teachers were more receptive to feedback and reflective practices when school heads fostered trust, open communication, and professional collaboration. Conversely, reflective practices were less effective when perceived as evaluative or punitive. School heads who approached supervision as a developmental process contributed to creating a safe, non-

threatening environment where teachers could engage meaningfully in reflection, implement recommendations, and continuously refine their instructional methods (Chin et al., 2022).

Instructional supervision positively influenced teacher performance by combining reflective practices, data-driven support, and a collaborative school culture. These practices strengthened teacher autonomy, enhanced instructional competence, and promoted professional growth, demonstrating that effective supervision is both a developmental and a performance-enhancing mechanism in education.

Instructional Leadership Training Design Based on Supervisory Practices

The study's findings on the instructional supervisory practices of school heads, their influence on teacher performance, and the development of a culture of continuous professional development provided a clear basis for designing an instructional leadership training program. The training is grounded in the principles of effective supervision, including structured classroom observation, individualized coaching and mentoring, data-driven instructional support, reflective practices, collaborative learning, and teacher-centered supervision. Translating these findings into a structured program, the training aims to strengthen the capacity of school heads to guide teachers effectively, foster professional growth, and promote a culture of sustained instructional excellence.

The program emphasizes data-driven instructional support as a core component, reflecting findings that school heads used performance data, classroom observations, and teacher evaluations to provide targeted, evidence-based guidance. This approach ensures that supervision is personalized, relevant, and aligned with professional development needs, enabling teachers to identify their strengths and areas for improvement while enhancing instructional quality. School heads are trained to integrate data into post-observation conferences and ongoing coaching, making feedback actionable and measurable.

Reflective practices and teacher autonomy are incorporated into the training design to promote professional self-assessment. School heads are guided to implement structured reflection in post-observation conferences, facilitating two-way dialogue with teachers, encouraging them to evaluate their instructional strategies, and fostering ownership of professional growth. This element of the training mirrors the study's findings that reflective practices enhance teacher efficacy, confidence, and motivation, particularly when embedded in a supportive, non-judgmental school culture (Sibomana, 2020; Maisyaroh et al., 2021; Chin et al., 2022).

The training also emphasizes building a culture of continuous professional development, where collaborative platforms such as Learning Action Cells (LACs), peer

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coaching, and mentorship programs are central. School heads are trained to facilitate teacher-centered supervision, guide collaborative learning, and mentor new or struggling teachers to strengthen instructional competence, confidence, and collaboration. Research indicates that teacher-centered supervision, mentorship, and collaborative professional communities improve instructional effectiveness, job satisfaction, and long-term teacher growth (Kilag & Sasan, 2023; Culajara, 2023; Zain et al., 2021; Ahn et al., 2023; Sibomana, 2020; Berkovich & Bogler, 2020).

In designing the training, attention is given to overcoming practical challenges such as time constraints, resource limitations, and ensuring consistent implementation of supervisory practices. School heads are provided with strategies to integrate supervision into their daily routines, manage workload effectively, and sustain professional development initiatives. By combining structured observation, data-informed feedback, reflective practices, mentorship, and teacher-centered approaches, the training equips school heads with a comprehensive set of tools to strengthen supervision, improve teacher performance, and embrace a culture of ongoing professional growth and instructional excellence.

a. Influence of Instructional Supervision on Teacher Performance. This theme indicates the direct role of instructional supervision in improving teacher performance. Based on the participants' narratives, supervision influenced teachers' classroom practices through constructive feedback, coaching, mentoring, reflective activities, and continuous monitoring. These supervisory actions helped teachers identify their strengths and areas for improvement, apply suggested strategies, and become more effective in lesson delivery and classroom management. The sub-themes under this category show how instructional supervision served as a mechanism for enhancing teachers' competence, confidence, and overall professional performance.

b. Feedback and Coaching for Professional Growth. Feedback and coaching became the key practices in instructional supervision, and school heads continued to offer customized guidance to enhance teaching practices and performance. These practices revolved around giving constructive feedback, setting clear expectations, and offering specific coaching to enable the teachers to develop their skills. One of the teachers explained how the school head's feedback was received as a real change in the teaching practice because they said, "*Ginagawa kong konkretong aksyon ang kanyang ma recommendations, tulad pag-revise ng lesson plan or paggamot ng mas angkop na teaching strategy.*" ("I turn his recommendations into concrete actions, such as revising my lesson plan or using a more appropriate teaching strategy.") This story reveals the practical experience of feedback where the teachers were not only provided with suggestions but also took action

according to the suggestions in their classroom activities, thus fostering the process of constant self-development.

Findings of the research indicate that school heads also focused on individualized support whereby coaching sessions were aimed at giving advice on areas of improvement. This individual treatment made sure feedback was applicable to the needs of individual teachers, be it the perfection of lesson plans or the improvement of classroom management techniques. Moreover, school heads ensured they followed up on their feedback so that the teachers could have time to reflect on their improvement and make appropriate corrections. It was this continuous feedback and coaching process that enabled the continued growth of the instructional abilities of teachers so that they could constantly improve their teaching strategies.

c. Mentorship for Newly Hired Teachers. One of the strategies that school heads applied to help new and struggling teachers was mentorship. These mentorship programs gave individual guidance and assistance to teachers yet to master their skills or to the profession's requirements. One of the principals stressed the need to have a mentorship by saying, "*Ang mentorship ay nakatulong lalo na sa mga bagong guro... sa tulong ng mga guro na mas marurunong, mas gumaling sila sa loob ng silid-aralan*" ("Mentorship is especially helpful for new teachers... with the help of more experienced teachers, they become more effective inside the classroom"). This story shows how mentoring, particularly by older and more experienced teachers, enabled young and ineffective teachers to become more effective through effective teaching, gain confidence, and deal better with their classrooms.

The findings of this study show that mentorship was quite important in helping to assimilate the new teachers and provide some relief to the struggling teachers. Mentors also offered practical advice, resources, and effective teaching practices, which helped the mentees to overcome the challenges. Not only was this strategy able to develop instructional expertise in the mentees but also enabled emotional and professional growth that provided the teachers with a feeling of support and capability. The mentorship, particularly for new teachers, helped them to settle better in the school system and helped in retaining the teachers better with a good support system.

d. Reflective Practices and Continuous Monitoring. Instructional supervision involved reflective practices and constant observations. School heads pointed out the need to follow up on feedback and have a successful implementation in the classroom. In explaining the follow-up process, one teacher said it worked out as follows: "*Bumabalik siya pagkatapos ng ilang araw para tingnan kung naipatupad ko ba as suggestions ang mga suggestions niya.*" ("He comes back after a few days to check whether I was able to implement his suggestions.") This assertion shows the

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continuity of the entire supervision process in which feedback was not only given but also observed to provide that improvement was being done. The frequent follow-up enabled the teachers to look back on their own practices, identify necessary changes to be made, and further develop themselves professionally.

The research results indicate that reflective practices and constant monitoring contributed to the development of a culture of accountability and professional development. The school heads were also able to give teachers sustained attention, which the teachers found very helpful since it gave them room to reflect on their teaching practice and see where they went wrong. This procedure assisted to guarantee that feedback could be practical, and also the teachers got the assistance they required to execute it properly. Constant observation also enabled the heads of schools to detect probable challenges at an early date and offer prompt help to avoid stagnation in the teaching practices.

f. Data-Driven Instructional Support. The use of data-driven instructional support featured prominently in the practice of instructional supervision of school heads. The school heads were utilizing the information that was obtained through classroom observations, student performance, and teacher evaluation to offer specific assistance and instruct on the improvement in the teaching. One of the head teachers said, “*Ang data-driven process ay nagagamit ko din sa pag-supervise ko sa mga teachers na hawak ko; nagkakaroon kami ng konkretong batayan sa pagbibigay ng feedback.*” (“I also use the data-driven process in supervising the teachers I handle... it gives us a concrete basis for providing feedback.”) This shows how the data usage was useful to offer concrete and evidence-based feedback by school heads so that the assistance offered to teachers could be relevant and targeted at areas of improvement.

The results indicate that the application of data to guide the instructional supervision practices allowed school heads to provide more constructive and individual feedback to teachers. Through the analysis of data on students' performance and teaching practices, school heads could determine certain aspects in which the teachers require assistance, and so their attention can be directed toward these aspects. This strategy made sure that it was not the teachers as a group but rather as individuals that the feedback would be generalized so that the interventions could be more specific and practical. The applications of the use of data also suggested a more objective and transparent method of instructional assistance, which increased accountability if teachers also obtained the required guidance to work better in their practices.

Support of Supervisory Practices to the Performance of Teachers

This theme emphasizes the supportive mechanisms embedded in supervisory practices that contribute to teachers' professional growth and improved performance. The findings revealed that beyond direct observation and evaluation, school heads also fostered collaboration, trust, and a positive environment where teachers felt encouraged to learn and improve. Through shared practices, collegial support, and a nurturing school culture, teachers were given opportunities to develop their skills in a more open and meaningful way. The sub-themes under this category demonstrate how supportive supervisory practices created conditions that enabled teachers to perform more effectively and grow professionally.

a. Collaborative Learning and Sharing Best Practices.

The instructional supervision practices followed collaborative forms of learning, including Learning Action Cells (LAC), peer coaching, and team teaching. Such practices gave the teachers the opportunity to collaborate, exchange their teaching strategies, and solve their shared challenges in a cooperative and amicable way. One of the teachers revealed, “*Sa LAC, pagkakakitaan numpung nagkakaroon nami ng pagbahagi ng best practices at mga challenges sa pagtuturo.*” (“In the Learning Action Cell, we are given opportunities to share best practices and the challenges we encounter in teaching.”) Another issue brought out in this story is the importance of LACs where teachers have an opportunity to meet, exchange ideas, and reflect on their teaching practice. These teaming areas did not only promote professional growth, but they also gave a high level of community to the teachers in these areas, where teachers assist each other and learn alongside each other.

According to the study results, the teacher involvement in LACs, peer coaching, and team teaching are significant variables that contributed to teacher professional development. Teachers have explained that they have seen themselves as more confident and competent teachers in the teaching practices after undertaking collaborative learning activities. The special emphasis was put on LACs that provided the teachers with the opportunity to share their experiences, discuss their instruction techniques, and to seek the most general solutions to the teaching issues. In these types of collaboration, teachers had the opportunity to develop their pedagogical practices, introduce new approaches, and get the ideas of the best practices as given by other teachers. This teamwork also encouraged reflective practice whereby teachers were at liberty to criticize their teaching and be reminded by their peers in a non-intimidating environment.

b. Supportive School Culture. An instructional supervision practice based on supporting and non-threatening school culture was one of the cornerstones of instruction. The

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school heads also did their best to ensure they provided a setting wherein teachers were free to experiment with new teaching methods and undertake professional growth without being subjected to judgment. One head teacher was asked, “*Ang pinakamalaking tulong o suportang ibinibigay namin ay ang kulturang kung saan ligtas ang pakiramdam ng mga guro na sumubok ng bagong bagay at mag-develop.*” (“The greatest help or support we provide is a culture where teachers feel safe to try new things and develop.”) This story reflects how the introduction of a conducive school culture enabled the teachers to feel safe to take risks, innovate, and pursue lifelong professional development.

The results show that a supportive school culture was important in promoting teacher engagement and growth. When teachers felt that the school heads and others supported them, they were more likely to engage in professional learning opportunities, embrace new teaching methods, and work with others. An open, non-threatening, and inclusive atmosphere contributed to lessening the stress and anxiety levels that usually follow formal evaluations, and teachers can concentrate on the betterment of their practice instead of worrying about appraisal. Such an atmosphere gave the teachers an opportunity to discuss the problems and find support, which eventually led to their professional development in the broader context.

The Development of Contextualized Training Design Based on Supervisory Practices

The results of the study underscored the critical role of school heads in improving teaching quality and fostering professional growth among teachers. Findings revealed that effective instructional supervision comprising structured classroom observation, individualized coaching and mentoring, and professional learning facilitation directly enhanced teacher performance. Instructional monitoring involved pre-conference, actual observation, and post-conference processes, ensuring systematic feedback and alignment with standards such as RPMS-PPST and MELCs. Coaching and mentoring provided personalized support, peer coaching opportunities, and ongoing guidance, while professional learning facilitation promoted collaborative planning, Learning Action Cells (LACs), and stakeholder engagement. Based on these findings, the general objective of the proposed program is to design an instructional leadership training for school heads that strengthens supervisory competencies and professional learning facilitation. The specific objectives include enhancing school heads’ abilities in delivering feedback and coaching, developing collaborative learning structures among teachers, and integrating data-driven approaches into instructional supervision.

Prior to implementation, the program will undergo a pre-implementation phase that involves document preparation, coordination with trainers, finalization of venue

and materials, participant invitations, and pre-training orientation. This ensures that all logistical and instructional resources are in place, providing a clear foundation for the training. Participants will receive preparatory materials and online resources to facilitate engagement and ensure they are familiar with the expectations and activities of the program. This phase also serves to communicate the goals of the training and the anticipated outcomes, preparing both participants and organizers for a focused and effective learning experience.

The training program is structured as a three-day blended learning initiative titled “Leading with Impact: Enhancing Instructional Supervision Practices for School Heads.” The primary mode is face-to-face, including role-playing, peer coaching simulations, classroom observation walkthroughs, and collaborative planning exercises, while online support supplements with pre-training orientation, resource sharing, post-training follow-ups, supervision plan submissions, and reflection journals. Day 1 focuses on instructional monitoring, covering structured classroom observation, standards-based instructional assessment, and feedback implementation and follow-up. Day 2 centers on coaching and mentoring, addressing individualized teacher support, peer coaching, collaborative reflection, and constructive feedback. Day 3 emphasizes professional learning facilitation, including collaborative planning through LACs, teacher empowerment and professional growth strategies, and engaging internal and external stakeholders. Target participants include 15 school heads, 4 mentoring staff, 5 support staff, and 1 organizer, with four resource persons, all of whom are highly qualified in instructional supervision, mentoring, and professional learning facilitation.

The program’s administrative support includes coordination with school and division offices, scheduling, venue preparation, and provision of training materials. Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms involve pre- and post-training assessments, evaluation forms, feedback sessions, follow-up coaching, and documentation of supervision plans and implementation outcomes. Budgetary requirements cover venue rental, meals and snacks, training materials, honoraria for resource persons, certificates and printing, and a contingency fund, with an estimated total of PHP 27,750. The source of funds will come from school and division professional development allocations, ensuring that all operational costs are supported and that the training can be implemented effectively without interruption.

Leading with Impact: Enhancing Instructional Supervision Practices for School Heads

The proposed Learning and Development (L&D) program entitled “Leading with Impact: Enhancing Instructional Supervision Practices for School Heads” is anchored on the findings of the study, which revealed the critical roles of instructional monitoring, individualized

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coaching, and collective professional learning in improving teaching quality. The rationale of this proposal stems from the need to strengthen school heads' competencies in instructional supervision. Particularly, the study highlights the need to strengthen clinical supervision and classroom observation, coaching, mentoring, technical assistance, collaborative supervision, and peer learning. These practices influence and support teacher performance through structured feedback, targeted assistance, and professional collaboration. While current practices are functional, there is a need to enhance data-driven decision-making, reflective coaching, and sustained professional learning to improve teaching effectiveness and learner outcomes.

Thus, this program aims to enhance school heads' knowledge and skills in clinical supervision and effective classroom observation; strengthen their capacity to provide coaching, mentoring, and technical assistance that support teacher development; develop their competence in facilitating collaborative supervision and peer learning, including LAC sessions and other professional learning structures; and promote a holistic approach to instructional leadership that integrates data-driven practices, reflective coaching, and continuous professional growth. The preliminaries of the proposal include its implementation during the summer vacation of School Year 2026–2027, a strategic schedule that ensures full participation without disrupting instructional time. The training will be conducted over a three-day period with 15 participants composed of school heads and instructional leaders, supported by 5 support staff/organizers who will manage logistics, documentation, and coordination; and 4 monitoring staff who will oversee implementation fidelity and evaluation processes. Prior to the training, preparatory activities will include needs assessment validation, finalization of training design, preparation of materials, and coordination with facilitators and stakeholders. Registration, orientation, and setting of expectations will be conducted on the first day to ensure clarity of objectives and smooth program flow.

The training design adopts a blended and interactive approach, integrating lectures, workshops, simulations, group discussions, case analyses, and reflective sessions. The program is structured into key thematic modules aligned with the study's findings. Day 1 will focus on instructional monitoring and policy adherence, covering topics such as clinical supervision processes (pre-conference, observation, and post-conference), alignment with RPMS-PPST and MELCs, and data-driven supervision using assessment data. Day 2 will center on coaching, mentoring, and technical assistance, including subtopics such as reflective feedback techniques, coaching models (e.g., partnership approach), mentoring systems for novice teachers, and designing individualized development plans. Day 3 will emphasize facilitation of collective professional learning, highlighting strategies in sustaining LAC sessions,

designing effective INSET programs, integrating 21st-century teaching approaches (e.g., Multimedia Integration for Data-Driven Instruction and Collaborative Learning), and promoting teacher wellness and resilience. The training will also include action planning sessions where participants will develop their own school-based instructional supervision enhancement plans. The target participants are school heads and instructional leaders, while resource persons may include experienced school principals, education supervisors, master teachers, and external experts in instructional leadership and professional development, ensuring both theoretical grounding and practical insights.

Administrative support is essential for the successful implementation of the program. Coordination with the Schools Division Office and relevant stakeholders will be undertaken to ensure alignment with institutional priorities and policies. The monitoring and evaluation (M&E) component will include pre- and post-training assessments, session evaluations, observation of participant engagement, and review of output-based deliverables such as action plans. Follow-up mechanisms, such as post-training coaching and progress monitoring, will also be established to ensure the sustainability of learning. Budgetary requirements will cover training materials, meals, certificates, honoraria for resource people, venue preparation, and other operational expenses. Funding sources may include the School Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE), division funds, and possible support from stakeholders or local government units, subject to existing government accounting and auditing rules. Transparency and accountability in fund utilization shall be strictly observed. Additional components of the proposal may include risk management strategies, documentation and reporting plans, and dissemination of best practices. Ultimately, this L&D initiative aims not only to enhance instructional supervision practices but also to cultivate transformative school leaders who can lead with impact, ensuring improved teaching quality and better learning outcomes for all students.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that the instructional supervisory practices of school heads are essential in shaping teacher performance and professional growth. Findings revealed that school heads consistently employed instructional monitoring, coaching, mentoring, learning facilitation, classroom observation, constructive feedback, and mentorship for the newly hired teachers, which are very essential instructional supports. The effectiveness of supervision was further enhanced when school heads adopted teacher-centered, joint problem-solving, and collaborative goal-setting. Nevertheless, challenges such as time constraints, heavy workloads, and varying supervisory competencies among school heads affected the uniformity

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and depth of supervision, highlighting the need for structured capacity-building interventions to strengthen instructional leadership skills.

Furthermore, the study recommends that the Schools Division Office and district supervisors may institutionalize ongoing structures to reinforce these practices. This includes periodic follow-up coaching for school heads, inter-leader learning sessions, and systematic monitoring of supervisory practices through clear indicators and evaluation tools. Sustained post-training support will reinforce reflective leadership, accountability, and consistent application of evidence-based supervision across schools. By providing this training and implementing institutional support mechanisms, school heads will be equipped to deliver regular, progressive, and teacher-focused supervision, facilitating long-term professional development for teachers and improved learning outcomes for students. Ultimately, institutionalizing such a training program and support system will help standardize instructional supervision, address current gaps, and ensure that the positive impacts on teacher performance and professional growth are sustained across the district.

VII. DISCLOSURE

We declare that we have no financial or material interests related to the research in this paper that could create a conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Albert, J. R. G., Basillote, L. B., Alinsunurin, J. P., Vizmanos, J. F. V., Muñoz, M. S., & Hernandez, A. C. (2023). *Sustainable Development Goal 4 on quality education for all: How does the Philippines fare and what needs to be done? Philippine Institute for Development Studies*. <https://doi.org/10.62986/dp2023.16>
2. Aquino, C., Afalla, B., & Fabelico, F. (2021). *Managing educational institutions: School heads' leadership practices and teachers' performance*. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education* 10(4), 1325. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i4.21518>
3. Arrieta, G. (2021). Curriculum evaluation: Inputs for principal's instructional leadership. *International Journal of Social Learning*, 1(2), 147-162. <https://doi.org/10.47134/ijsl.v1i2.45>
4. Beach, D. M., & Reinhartz, J. (2000). *Supervisory leadership: Focus on instruction*. Allyn & Bacon.
5. Bell, C. A., Dobbelaer, M. J., Klette, K., & Visscher, A. J. (2019). Qualities of classroom observation systems. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 30(1), 3–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243453.2018.1539014>
6. Buban, L. M., & Digo, G. S. (2021). Management beliefs and practices of elementary school heads on instructional leadership. *International Journal of Research - GRANTHAALAYAH*, 9(7), 170-178.
7. Byrne, D. (2021). *A worked example of Braun and Clarke's approach to reflexive thematic analysis*. *Quality & Quantity*, 56, 1391–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-021-01182-y>.
8. Chen, J., Li, D., & Xu, J. (2022). Sustainable development of EFL teachers' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) Situated in Multiple Learning Activity Systems. *Sustainability*, 14(14), 8934. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14148934>
9. Chin, J., Ching, G., Castillo, F., Wen, T., Huang, Y., Castillo, C., ... & Trajera, S. (2022). Perspectives on the barriers to and needs of teachers' professional development in the Philippines during COVID-19. *Sustainability*, 14(1), 470. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010470>
10. Collie, R. J. (2021). Teacher wellbeing and professional engagement: The role of school leadership and collaboration. *Educational Psychology*, 41(3), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2020.1829643>
11. Culajara, C. (2023). Improving teachers' professional development through School Learning Action Cell (SLAC). *Journal of Research Policy & Practice of Teachers & Teacher Education*, 13(1), 76-88. <https://doi.org/10.37134/jrpppte.vol13.1.6.2023>
12. Darling-Hammond, L., & Gu, Q. (2010). *The new lives of teachers*. Routledge.
13. Datnow, A., & Park, V. (2018). *Professional collaboration with purpose: Teacher learning toward equitable and excellent schools*. Routledge.
14. Department of Education. (2020). *National adoption and implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH)* (DepEd Order No. 024, s. 2020). Department of Education.
15. Department of Education. (2015). DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015: *Guidelines on the establishment and implementation of the results-based performance management system (RPMS) in the Department of Education*. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wpcontent/uploads/2015/02/DO_s2015_02.pdf
16. DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017
Department of Education. (2017). *DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017: National adoption and implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)*. Department of Education.

Chrysler S. Balmes et al., Instructional Supervisory Practices and their Support of Teacher Performance: Basis for the Development of a Training Program

- <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2017/08/11/do-42-s-2017->
17. Department of Education. (2020). *DepEd Order No. 024, s. 2020: National adoption and implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for School Heads (PPSSH)*. Department of Education. <https://naro.law.upd.edu.ph/documents/1348>
 18. Diano, F. and Calbi, J. (2024). School heads' leadership styles: Impact on organizational innovativeness and performance of public elementary schools in the new normal. *Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science Journal*, 5(2), 410-425. <https://doi.org/10.47175/rielsj.v5i2.944>
 19. Gärtner, H. (2017). *Classroom observations and teacher evaluation: Methods and practices in educational supervision*. Springer.
 20. Goldhammer, R. (1969). *Clinical supervision: Special methods for the supervision of teachers*. Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
 21. Harries, I. (2024). The supervision of experienced secondary school-based counselors: A situational analysis and constructivist grounded theory exploration of best practice. *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research*, 25(2). <https://doi.org/10.1002/capr.12842>
 22. Joyce, B., & Showers, B. (2002). *Student achievement through staff development* (3rd ed.). ASCD.
 23. Kilag, O. and Sasan, J. (2023). Unpacking the role of instructional leadership in teacher professional development. *Advanced Qualitative Research*, 1(1), 63-73. <https://doi.org/10.31098/aqr.v1i1.1380>
 24. Kipasika, D. (2024). Instructional supervision and teacher performance in schools. *International Journal of Educational Leadership*, 12(2), 45–58.
 25. Knight, J. (2007). *Instructional coaching: A partnership approach to improving instruction*. Corwin Press.
 26. Kraft, M. A., Blazar, D., & Hogan, D. (2018). The effect of teacher coaching on instruction and achievement: A meta-analysis of the causal evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 88(4), 547–588. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654318759268>
 27. Lualhati, G., & Karanjakwut, P. (2025). Peer coaching and teachers' instructional performance in Philippine schools. *Asia Pacific Journal of Educational Research*, 8(1), 22–36.
 28. Maisyaroh, M., Wiyono, B., Hardika, H., Valdez, A., Mangorsi, S., & Canapi, S. (2021). The implementation of instructional supervision in Indonesia and the Philippines and its effect on the variation of teacher learning models and materials. *Cogent Education*, 8(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2021.1962232>.
 29. Montales, J. C., & Digo, G. S. (2024). Correlational study on the performance of school heads and their instructional leadership practices. *International Journal of Social Science and Education Research Studies*, 4(3), 199–206. <https://doi.org/10.55677/ijssers/V04I3Y2024-05>.
 30. Morales, M. (2023). Practices, challenges, and perceived impact of professional development activities among senior high school teachers. *Cognizance Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(12), 136-150. <https://doi.org/10.47760/cognizance.2023.v03i12.012>
 31. Naparan, G. B., & Tulod, R. G. (2021). Time management strategies of school administrators towards effective administration: A phenomenological study. *The New Educational Review*, 63(1), 59–68. <https://doi.org/10.15804/tner.21.63.1.05>
 32. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). (2020). *Teachers and school leaders as lifelong learners: TALIS 2018 results* (Volume I). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/1d0bc92a-en>
 33. Pomentel, L. (2024). Exploring the influence of school heads' instructional supervision on teachers' efficacy and performance. *International Journal of Research Publications*, 148(1). <https://doi.org/10.47119/ijrp1001481520246420>
 34. Poortman, C. L., & Schildkamp, K. (2016). Solving student achievement problems with a data use intervention for teachers. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 60, 425–433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tate.2016.06.010>
 35. Ramadhona, A., et al. (2025). Instructional coaching and teacher professional growth: A systematic review. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*, 15(1), 55–72.
 36. Republic Act No. 9155. (2001). *Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001*. *Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines*. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2001/08/11/republic-act-no-9155/>
 37. Salva, R. A., Cadavedo, L. O., Cadavedo, S. V. O., & Patinga, K. T. (2023). Technology-assisted and in-person supervisory challenges in Philippine public schools: A comparative analysis. *The New Educational Review*, 72(2), 148–158. <https://doi.org/10.15804/tner.23.72.2.11>
 38. Schildkamp, K., & Ehren, M. (2013). From “intuitive” to “data-informed” decision-

Chrysler S. Balmes et al., Instructional Supervisory Practices and their Support of Teacher Performance: Basis for the Development of a Training Program

- making in Dutch secondary schools? *Professional Development in Education*, 39(4), 581–598. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2012.751084>
39. Sibomana, I. (2020). Perceptions of teachers on the instructional leadership behaviors of secondary school principals in Rwanda. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 50(1), 64–80. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143220938365>
 40. Tan, C., Dimmock, C., & Walker, A. (2021). How school leadership practices relate to student outcomes: Insights from a three-level meta-analysis. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 52(1), 6–27. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17411432211061445>
 41. Tan, C., et al. (2022). Data-driven instructional supervision and teacher development in schools. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 60(4), 410–425.
 42. Tuytens, M., & Devos, G. (2017). Teacher evaluation policy as perceived by teachers and school leaders: Effects on professional development and school improvement. *Teachers and Teaching*, 23(6), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13540602.2017.1287695>
 43. Vangrieken, K., Dochy, F., Raes, E., & Kyndt, E. (2017). Teacher collaboration: A systematic review. *Educational Research Review*, 15, 17–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2015.04.002>
 44. Zain, A., Asimiran, S., Razali, A., & Ahmad, N. (2021). Coaching and mentoring as a teaching supervision approach in secondary school. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 11(4S), 98. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v11i4s.19233>